
CONTRIBUTION OF UGC IN PROMOTING ACADEMIC LIBRARIES SERVICES

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H. W. Beecher –

A Library is not a luxury but
one of the necessities of life.

Abstract:

UGC is a statutory organization set up for the determination and maintenance of standards of higher education in India. UGC initiated Major project under the IUCAA, Information and Library Network (INFLIBNET) Centre. INFLIBNET is involved to support teaching and research in higher education and modernizing university and college libraries in India. The e-ShodhSindhu provide access to current as well as archives of more than 10,000 core and peer-reviewed journals and a number of bibliographic, citation and factual databases in different disciplines. This paper describe role of UGC in higher education, financial support and collection development, Institutional Library network in academic libraries.

Keywords: UGC, Academic Libraries, Education, Library Network

Introduction:

Library is the core of a Institution. As a resource it occupies the central and primary place, because it serves all the functions of institution, teaching and research, the creation of new knowledge and the transmission of posterity of the learning. After the independence the development of modern academic libraries is well connected with the progress of academic institution in country. The UGC provides funds to government recognized universities and colleges libraries under 2(f) and 12(B) in different heads such as purchase of Books, Journals, Equipment, infrastructure development, Construction of library Building etc. The UGC has

contributed mostly for the College and University libraries to improve the quality of Higher Education. As on 31.03.2021, the 982 Universities, 54 Central, 425 State Public, 375 State Private, 125 Deemed to be Universities, 3 Institutions established under State Legislation and 12717 Colleges are listed under Section 2(f) and out of these colleges 10143 colleges are under Section 12(B) in the Higher Education.

Objectives of the Study:

The main objective of this paper is to review the roll of UGC in promoting of academic libraries services to improvement of higher education Indian

and financial assistant for acquisition of books, periodicals and identify the Remote access Library Network.

Research Methodology:

In this study researcher used secondary data and descriptive research methodology technique for the research purpose.

Academic Libraries and Higher Education:

The library plays a very essential role in education process. The library is a heart of that academic institution which actively performs the activities related to learning and teaching research gathers of new knowledge, dissemination of result and conservation of knowledge and ideas along with the extension of services.

The “Kothari Commission report” (1964-66) on education to role of libraries in higher education is reflected in these words, no new university, college or department should be setup without taking into account its library needs in terms of staff, books, journals, space etc. “Nothing could be more damaging to a growing department than to neglect its library or to give it a low priority. On the contrary, the library should be an important centre of attraction on the college or university campus.”

The academic libraries include school, college, university and research libraries. All these cater to the needs of the academic community for supplementing the study and search programmes of the institution and help conserve and disseminate knowledge. The UGC has contributed mostly for the College and University libraries to improve the quality of Higher Education.

University Grant Commission:

The University Grants Commission (UGC) Act was passed by parliament in March 1956, coordination of Higher Education and for determination and maintenance of standards of teaching, examination and research in universities and provides grants to the universities and academics. Increasing number of students and research scholar in higher education and increasing in the needs all kinds of facilities. There is some function and role of UGC are given below.

1. UGC and Library Committee
2. UGC and Academic Libraries
3. UGC and Scale of Library staff
4. UGC and Library Science Training
5. UGC and Reprographic Service
6. UGC and Computers
7. Establishment of INFLIBNET

Library Committee:

In the year of 1957, the Library committee was established under the chairmanship of S.R. Ranganathan to look into the functioning of academic libraries. The Govt. of India had decided to seek advice from a professional librarian regarding university libraries. The Committee reviewed the library services in their totality and made and made recommendations for UGC grants, library funds, book selection and book purchases, promotion of reading habit, weeding out the loss of books, documentation, library staff, library building and for systematic development of university and college libraries in the country.

Financial Support to Academic Libraries:

UGC support financial assistance is given to all types of Universities and Government and affiliated colleges, which receive grants for expansion of libraries

facilities so as to meet the demands of the student's teachers and research scholars. The commission provides adequate and appropriate grants for various schemes, Regional Library Centers, Library Building, National Information Centers, Collection development. The acquisition of books and journals and provides high speed VPN Internet connections so as to have electronic access to academic information. For other infrastructural facilities also like library buildings furniture and equipment grants are given in every five-year plan period it also introduced a scheme of book bank in Government and affiliated colleges and universities by providing grants to acquire multiple copies of costly text books recommended in all the disciplines.

Institutional Library Network:

The UGC has played an important role in the improvement of university and college libraries. Realizing the value of the library and its role in higher education, the UGC accepted most of the recommendations of the several committees and commissions. UGC provides financial assistance for collection development, acquisition of books, periodicals and required literature of the library. Working groups on information and library networks, modernization of library service and information centres, and the developmental programmes of NISSAT, NIC, DESIMET, ERNET, CALNET, DELNET and CIRNET have covered things like standardization of information handling, networks, and training.

Information and Library Network (INFLIBNET):

In March 1991 UGC initiated Major project under the IUCAA,

Information and Library Network (INFLIBNET) Centre. INFLIBNET is involved to support teaching and research in higher education and modernizing university libraries in India. INFLIBNET is set out to be a major player in promoting scholarly communication among academicians and researchers in India. Also it promotes automation, creates union catalogues, provides access to information sources, provides training, etc. INFLIBNET has developed "SOUL" (Software for University Libraries) software for automation in-house functions.

1. e-ShodhSindhu: Consortium:

In 2015, the MHRD merged the three consortia initiatives, namely UGC-INFONET Digital Library Consortium, NLIST and INDEST-AICTE Consortium in e-ShodhSindhu. The e-ShodhSindhu provide access to current as well as archives of more than 7.096 peer-reviewed e-journals and 6Lakh+e-books (through NDLI) to more than 449 institutions that include universities. Nlist is a college component that provide access to 6150 e-journals and 7,64,300+ e-books to more than 4.10 lakh users.

Aims and Objectives:

The main objective of the e-ShodhSindhu: Consortia for Higher Education E-Resources is to provide access to qualitative electronic resources including full-text, bibliographic and factual databases to academic institutions at a lower rates of subscription. The major aims and objectives of the e-Shodh Sindhu are as follows:

- ❖ Setting-up e-ShodhSindhu: Consortia for Higher Education E-Resources by augmenting and strengthening activities and services offered by three MHRD-funded Consortia;

- ❖ Develop a formidable collection of e-journals, e-journal archives and e-books on perpetual access basis;
- ❖ Monitor and promote usage of e-resources in member universities, colleges and technical institutions in India through awareness and training programmes;
- ❖ Provide access to subscription-based scholarly information (e-books and e-journals) to all educational institutions;
- ❖ Provide access to scholarly content available in open access through subject portals and subject gateways;
- ❖ Bridge digital divide and move towards an information-rich society;
- ❖ Provide access to selected e-resources to additional institutions including open universities and MHRD-funded institutions that are not covered under existing consortia;
- ❖ Take-up additional activities and services that require collaborative platform and are not being performed by existing Consortia; and
- ❖ Moving towards developing a National Electronic Library with electronic journals and electronic books as its major building blocks.

2. *INDIAN Access Management Federation (INFED)* –

The INDIAN Access Management Federation (INFED) has adopted Shibboleth, a standard-based open source software, for authenticating authorized users from institutions and provide them seamless access to e-resources from anywhere, anytime. Shibboleth offers a

mechanism for users to access multiple resources within a federated single sign-on framework. The INFED allow users to access internal and external resources seamlessly using a single, institutionally controlled identity, for authenticating authorized users Universities and Colleges and providing them seamless access to e-resources from anywhere, anytime. Currently, 183 institutions have joined INFED and 37 publishers have jointed and provide the services.

Benefits of INFED:

- ❖ Access to e-resources anytime, anywhere, any device.
- ❖ Member institutions will get off-campus access of their subscribed resources if the respective service provider is a part of INFED.
- ❖ Institute can provide protected content to multiple organizations using a single authentication framework.
- ❖ The home institution can control when an identity disclosed, and how much information is revealed.
- ❖ Web-based distributed authentication and authorization services can be used for any other purpose beyond e-resources.

3. *CSIR E-Journals Consortium* –

CSIR has also formed a consortium with the National Institute of Science, Communication and Information Resources (NISCAIR) (formed by merging INSDOC and NISCOM) as nodel agencies. To add to CSIR's research and development activities, NISCAIR implements and agents access to electronic journals. On behalf of CSIR, he has signed an agreement with Elsevier to access 1,500 electronic journals and intends to subscribe for more.

Conclusion:

UGC has finance supported to universities and government college libraries, for purchase of Books, Journals and equipments for libraries, which is definitely benefited to them. On the other side INFLIBNET is involved to support to provide e-shodhSindhu library Consortia for Higher Education. Library Consortia provide access to qualitative electronic resources including full-text, bibliographic and factual databases to academic institutions at a lower rates of subscription. These databases benefit to students, teachers and research scholar accessing useful resources.

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